

ISic3364

I.Sicily inscription 3364

Language

Sikel

Type

(?)

Material

sandstone

Object

block

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Mendolito

Place of origin (modern)

Mendolito

Provenance

Found in excavation by Pelagatti 1962 in east wall of the city gate,
inside the fortifications

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644869

Bibliography

Agostiniani, L. 2009. L'iscrizione della porta urbica del Mendolito. In Ancillotti, A., Calderini, A.(eds.), *La città italica. Atti del II Convegno Internazionale sugli Antichi Umbri, Gubbio, 25-27 settembre 2003*. Perugia. pp. 35-52.

Agostiniani, L. 1992. Les parlers indigenes de la Sicile pregreccque. *Lalies*. 11:

126-157.

Albanese, R.M. 1991. Mendolito. In Nenci, G., Vallet, G.(eds.), *Bibliografia topografica della colonizzazione greca in Italia e nelle isole tirreniche*. Pisa. pp. 545-561. At 546 no.4

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